

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF THE TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF BASALT TEXTILE AT VARIOUS STRAIN RATES

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the mechanical properties of the textile component of textile-reinforced mortars (TRM) is critical since they directly influence the composite's ultimate tensile strength and pseudo-ductile behaviour. This study explores the tensile behaviour of a bi-directional basalt textile at dynamic strain rates using a high-speed servo-hydraulic machine with specialised grips and the digital image correlation technique. The experimental approach, challenges, and strain rate effect on the textile's mechanical properties are described in detail. Three numerical models are developed using the Abaqus/CAE software and are verified with the experimental results. The models are also compared in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency.

KEYWORDS

Tensile tests; textile-reinforced mortar; basalt textile; dynamic strain rates; numerical modelling; finite element

INTRODUCTION

Textiles are an essential part of our society and continue to drive innovation and advancements in materials science. They have been integral to the aerospace (Li et al., 2022), automotive (Sezgin & Berkalp, 2018), and marine industries (Singha & Singha, 2012), and their uses in soft robotics applications are growing (Fu et al., 2022). In civil engineering, common textile applications include soil reinforcement (Wu et al., 2020) and tensile reinforcement in concrete and retrofitting composites (Venigalla et al., 2022). Among these applications, textile-reinforced mortar (TRM) composites remain one of the least explored uses despite acclaimed benefits of high-strength-to-weight ratio, crack control, enhanced energy absorption and impact resistance, and fire and thermal durability. This paper focuses on textiles used in TRM composites – a state-of-the-art retrofitting technique.

Understanding the dynamic mechanical properties of TRM and their constituent materials is crucial for accurate designs and efficient structural strengthening of those structures prone to loading events such as earthquakes, hurricanes, crash impacts, and explosions. Knowledge of the mechanical characteristics of TRM textiles is necessary since it directly affects the mechanical performance and durability of TRM composites (Dong et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2019).

In general, acquiring reliable and accurate data to characterise the dynamic mechanical behaviour of materials is no easy task. Challenges relating to specimen and clamping, instrumentation, synchronisation, and data acquisition and analysis are often reported (Elmahdy & Verleysen, 2018; Fan et al., 2017; Spronk et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2011). Numerous researchers have conducted dynamic tensile tests on textiles and yarns, providing insights into their rate-sensitive mechanical characteristics. For instance, a study by Bai et al. (2020) examined how polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fibre bundles behaved under various strain rates, including 1/600, 40, 80, 120, and 160/s. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2016) investigated the dynamic response of a basalt fibre-reinforced polymer, ranging from 19 to 133/s. Yao et al. (2016) also investigated plain-woven aramid, glass, basalt, carbon, and unidirectional textiles at 25, 50, and 100/s. Furthermore, Ou, Zhu, Zhang, et al. (2016) studied basalt fibre yarn and fibre-reinforced polymer under a range of strain rates, notably 40, 80, 120, and 160/s. Lastly, L. Zhu et al.

(2012) investigated the characteristics of basalt filament tows moving between 600 and 3000/s. Most of these studies investigated fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) textiles - fibre sheets impregnated with a polymer matrix. Research on bi-directional, open-mesh textiles used in textile-reinforced concrete or mortar is lacking. One study by Zhu et al. (2011) considered the tensile behaviour of Alkali-resistant (AR) glass, polyethylene (PE) and carbon TRM textiles within the range of 9-28/s. The glass and carbon textiles demonstrated a linear elastic behaviour with brittle failure, whereas the PE material displayed ductile behaviour. This study also reported that specimen types deemed suitable for static loading testing were incompatible with dynamic loading conditions. The dynamic characteristics of TRM textiles made from other fibres remains unclear. Moreover, testing guidelines or recommendations for investigating these materials are unavailable.

Regarding TRM textile numerical modelling, several macroscopic models were developed to model static behaviour (Donnini et al., 2019; Grande & Milani, 2021; Monaco et al., 2019; Tran et al., 2020). However, to the author's knowledge, there have been no previous efforts to model the dynamic tensile behaviour of TRM textiles. Bayraktar and Hökelekli (2021) modelled a glass fibre textile as part of their TRM retrofitted minarets under seismic loading, and Mercedes et al. (2021) modelled masonry walls retrofitted hemp, cotton and glass fibre textiles under cyclic loads. However, both of these studies developed models with the static properties of the textiles.

Research is being carried out at Queen's University Belfast to advance knowledge on basalt textile-reinforced mortars (BTRM) at dynamic loading rates. This paper presents a portion of the work undertaken on the experimental tensile behaviour of a basalt fibre textile and basalt TRM composites at dynamic strain rates. Dynamic testing is done using a high-speed servo-hydraulic machine with specialised grips. Strain measurements are obtained by applying the digital image correlation technique. The experimental approach, challenges, and the effect of strain rate on the textile's mechanical properties are described in detail. In addition, three finite element (FE) models of the textile's dynamic tensile behaviour are developed using the Abaqus/CAE software. The accuracy of each model is then verified using the experimental outcomes. These models will serve as the basis for the future development of numerical models of the dynamic behaviour of BTRM composites, and BTRM retrofitted beams under impact loading.

METHOD

Material

The basalt textile is a 6mm squared mesh consisting of orthogonal warp and weft rovings (Figure 1). The textile is coated with an alkali-resistant chemical and has an equivalent thickness, mass density and weight of 0.039mm, 2.75g/cm³, and 250g/m², respectively. According to the manufacturer's data, it has an elastic modulus of 89GPa, a tensile strength of 60kN/m, and a 1.8% elongation at failure.

Figure 1: Basalt textile

Dynamic tensile test method

The dynamic tensile tests were conducted at the Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering (INEGI), Portugal, using a high-rate servo-hydraulic testing machine which can operate within a range of 1 - 1100mm/s with a load capacity of 20 kN. The tensile load was recorded at 75000 fps, and images were acquired at 3800 fps using a Photron SA3 high-speed camera and one

halogen spotlight. The camera was placed perpendicular to the surface of the specimen to capture its displacement and failure behaviour.

Initially, it was intended for the tests to be carried out using clamp grips and aluminium tabbed coupon specimens, as shown in Figure 2a and b. Quasi-static tests conducted by Carozzi et al. (2017); D’Anna et al. (2020) established that this type of specimen effectively distributes the gripping load and avoids specimen failure at the gripping areas. However, after numerous attempts, the specimens failed by the sliding of one or more rovings from the gripping section, as shown in Figure 2b. In order to ensure a valid specimen failure and uniform gripping force distribution, a set of specialised grips was developed (Figure 2c). With the specialised grips, no indication of stress concentrations was observed in the region where the textile was wrapped around the grips. However, it was important to align the specimens properly, as non-longitudinally aligned (slanted) grids led to failure initiation in the grip region, resulting in a reduction in tensile strength. The textile folds over the grips and ends between the two jaws, as shown in Figure 2d. With increasing tension on the specimen, the clamping force becomes stronger. The specimens were cut at 490mm lengths and spanned a width of approximately 26.7mm (to include four warped rovings). They were aligned between the top and bottom grips with a 100mm gauge length. Four specimens were tested at $2 \times 10^0/s$ (1000mm/s) and two at $2 \times 10^{-1}/s$ (100mm/s) loading rates through displacement-controlled loading. Additional tests not reported in this paper were carried out at 500mm/s. These loading rates fall within the induced shock/blast dynamic range and outside the 9-3000/s range explored in the previous studies concerning yarns and textiles. Specimens tested at the $10^0/s$ rate and $10^{-1}/s$ were labelled with the prefixes ‘X+0’ and ‘X-1’, respectively.

Figure 2: Types of grips and specimen types

Numerical approach

Three-dimensional models were implemented using the Abaqus/CAE finite element analysis software (Dassault Systèmes, 2021). The finite element (FE) models were verified using the experimental results obtained from the dynamic tensile tests at 0.2/s and 2/s strain rates. Three FE models were developed M1-Wire (Figure 3a), M2-Lamina (Figure 3b) and M3-Grid (Figure 4). M1 and M2 are simplified models of the textile. M1 was conceptualised as a ‘wire’ feature in Abaqus since the roving’s equivalent thickness (0.039mm) is considered small compared to its length.

In contrast, M2 and M3 were idealised as shells, given that the textile’s thickness is small compared to the width and length dimensions. M1 consists of four wires, each having a cross-sectional area of 0.261mm^2 , representing only the rovings in the warp direction. M2-Lamina is a 26.8mm wide rectangular lamina representing the warp and weft textile properties.

The M3-Grid model presents a new approach, which considers the actual geometry of the textile. Weft rovings were placed on the surface of warp rovings, similar to the textile (Figure 1 and Figure 4a), and are bonded by the Abaqus ‘merge’ feature, which assumes a perfect bond at the joints. Partitions were

created at the common interfaces of the merged weft and warp roving instances to retain distinct parts. This method is straightforward and averts the need for computationally expensive tie constraints (Dassault Systèmes, 2021) that would otherwise be needed to merge nodes of the weft and warp rovings. Measurements obtained with a micrometre were used to define the width and centre-to-centre spacing of the rovings as 1.6mm and 6.7mm, respectively. All models have the same length of 100mm, representing the free length between the grips at the beginning of the tests.

Figure 3: Simplified FE models

Figure 4: M3-Grid model

M1-Wire is discretised using 3D 2-node linear stress/displacement truss elements (T3D2), while M2-Lamina and M3-Grid are discretised using reduced integration 4-node quadrilateral continuum shell elements (S4R). An elastic-isotropic material behaviour is prescribed to M1 since only the axial deformation along the warp length is considered. M2 and M3 material behaviours are described as elastic-lamina with orthotropic elasticity in plane stress. Material properties are defined in three mutually perpendicular axes – the textile's warp, weft, and thickness directions. This plane stress behaviour assumes that the stress state is negligible in the thickness direction. Therefore, the elastic moduli, shear moduli and Poisson ratio are only defined for the textile's weft and warp directions. M3's elastic modulus in the weft direction is assumed to be 0.4% E_1 , as Monaco et al. (2020) suggested for the same textile. However, when this assumption was used in M2, it resulted in excessively distorted elements. Accordingly, the model was implemented using $E_2=E_1$. The textile's Poisson ratio is set as 0.35, and shear moduli were calculated using Eq.1 to Eq.3 below.

$$G_{12} = \frac{E_1}{2} \cdot (1 + \nu_{12}) \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

$$G_{13} = \frac{E_1}{2} \cdot (1 + \nu_{13}) \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$G_{23} = \frac{E_2}{2} \cdot (1 + \nu_{23}) \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

In the dynamic experimental tensile testing, the top grip remained fixed while the bottom grip applied the load by moving downwards. To simulate a similar condition, all specimen models were subjected to an axial displacement load at one end and a longitudinal translational constraint at the other. The load was applied over the average period derived from the experimental tests. All the material parameters used in the FE models are inputted according to the experimental and other calculated results in Table 1. Mesh sizes for all the models are also listed.

Table 1: Basalt textile Abaqus models input data

Model	$\dot{\epsilon}$	Input							Mesh size [mm]
		ρ [tonne/mm ³]	ν/ν_{12} ν_{13}/ν_{23}	E ₁ [MPa]	E ₂ [MPa]	G ₁₂ [MPa]	G ₁₃ [MPa]	G ₂₃ [MPa]	
M1	0.2	2.75E-09	0.35	73200	-	-	-	-	2
	2			54174	-	-	-	-	
M2	0.2			73200	73200	27111	27111	27111	2.5
	2			54174	54174	20265	20265	20265	
M3	0.2			73200	293	27111	27111	108	2
	2			54174	217	20265	20265	81	

$\dot{\epsilon}$ -strain rate, ρ -Mass density; $\nu, \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}$ – Poisson ratio; E/E₁ -Young's modulus in the warp direction; E₂ - Young's modulus in the weft direction; G₁₂, G₁₃, G₂₃ – shear modulus

The numerical analyses were performed with the Abaqus Explicit solver, which is ideal for modelling high-speed, short-duration events, and considers inertia effects and accelerations (Boulbes, 2019). The models were also run in Abaqus/Standard for comparison, and the results indicated that the inertia forces were negligible.

The computational analyses were carried out on an 11th Gen Intel Core i7-11800H 2.30GHz processor with 32GB of RAM. Each model's computational cost was expressed in terms of 'CPU time' and 'wall clock time'. CPU time is the time the CPU spends executing a code and conducting computations for the Abaqus analysis, while wall clock time provides a full measure of the time required for an Abaqus simulation, including the waiting time for input/output procedures to complete (Dassault Systèmes, 2021).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Displacement and strain-rate

Displacement measurements were extracted from the captured images using the GOM Correlate software. Strain values were calculated using displacement data from the specimens' surfaces and virtual gauge lengths, making the analysis independent of the effect of friction and slippage in the grip region (Luyckx et al., 2014). The strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) was determined from the slope of the strain-time plot of each specimen (Figure 5a).

The strain was also obtained from the grips to quantify slip. Slippage, determined as the difference between the grip's movement and the displacement of the textile itself, was greater than 70% of the overall movement of the grips (Figure 5b).

Stress-strain behaviour

Tensile stress was calculated by dividing the force by the product of the textile's equivalent thickness (0.039mm), number of warp rovings (4), and spacing between warp rovings (6.7mm). Stress-strain curves (Figure 6) were then developed using the strain and stress values, followed by the elastic moduli (E) from the slopes. Typically, the specimens exhibited linear elasticity up until the point of failure.

The results in Figure 6 and Table 2 demonstrate that the tensile mechanical properties of the basalt textile vary with the rate at which it is subjected to external loading. The tensile strength was marginally reduced as the strain rate increased from 10⁻¹/s to 10⁰/s. In contrast, the ultimate strain increased by approximately 0.75%. Ou, Zhu, Zhang, et al. (2016), D. Zhu et al. (2012) and Ou, Zhu and Li (2016) all reported similar trends of the effect of strain rate on the ultimate strain.

Figure 5: Strain-time plots

The declining gradients of the stress-strain plots suggest that the textile's stiffness is reduced with an increasing strain rate. A comparison of the dynamic results and quasi-static results (manufacturer's data and a previous study carried out at Queen's University (D'Anna et al., 2021)) shows that the textile is stiffer under static loadings. This finding contradicts previous studies on basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (Ou, Zhu, & Li, 2016; Yao et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2016) and basalt yarn (L. Zhu et al., 2012) which concluded that an increased strain rate increases stiffness. A plausible explanation for this anomaly may be due to the difference in structural configuration and coating of the basalt TRM textile compared to that of the basalt FRP and yarn materials (Ou, Zhu, & Li, 2016). In addition, when the basalt TRM is subjected to high strain rates, there may be a change in the energy dissipation mechanism (filament slippage) that leads to a loss of rigidity (Martínez-Hergueta et al., 2015). Given that the friction coefficient of polymer materials decreases as the sliding speed or loading rate increases (Dewan Muhammad & Mohammad Asaduzzaman, 2012; Wang et al., 2011), reduced friction between the textile and grips may have also contributed to the observed decrease in stiffness.

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves

Table 2: Dynamic tensile mechanical properties of basalt grid

Specimen ID	Strain rate [1/s]	Ultimate Strength [MPa]	Ultimate Strain [%]	Elastic Modulus [GPa]
X-1_1	0.21	2150	2.90	74.1
X-1_2	0.23	1878	2.60	72.3
Mean (COV%)	0.22 (6.4)	2014 (9.5)	2.75 (7.7)	73.2 (1.7)
X+0_1	1.86	1941	3.30	58.1
X+0_2	1.97	2113	4.10	52.1
X+0_3	2.29	1809	3.20	56.9
X+0_4	2.18	1799	3.30	55.2
Mean (COV%)	2.07 (9.4)	1915 (7.7)	3.50 (11.7)	55.4 (4.7)

Failure

Figure 7 depicts the typical progression of specimen failure. At both strain rates, minor deviations from linearity were observed closer to the beginning of the experiments, before points P1 and P4. The images corresponding to these points did not depict any discernible textile deterioration. At P2 and P5, the specimens were at ultimate stress; at P3 and P6, they failed due to roving breakage, the predominant failure mode.

Figure 7: Stress-strain response for specimens X-1_1 and X+0_1

Figure 8 shows that all samples failed within the specimens' gauge length region. Damage was initiated in the external rovings when the applied load exceeded the fibre's ultimate tensile strength, and then failure progressed to the middle two rovings. Specimens tested at 0.2/s took an average of 130ms, about eight times longer, to fail than those tested at 2/s (Figure 7).

Figure 8: Specimen failure mode

Effect of grip material on dynamic tensile behaviour

Textile movement within the grips was observed, possibly due to inadequate friction between the surface of the coated textile and the smooth stainless steel grip surface. To overcome this issue, the grip contact area was wrapped in 2mm rubber, as seen in Figure 9a. This undertaking resulted in premature failure near the top and bottom grip areas (Figure 10b). The rubber may have introduced excessive resistance between the grips and the specimen due to its high coefficient of friction. A follow-up decision was then made to remove half of the rubber (Figure 9b) to reduce the effects of excessive friction.

a) Rubber – fully covered b) Rubber – partially covered
Figure 9: Grip material and coverage

Figure 10 shows that the stainless steel surface allowed for smooth elastic behaviour and failure in the gauge length region of the specimens. However, discontinuities and jumps in the stress-strain behaviours were common when the grip area was partially and fully covered with rubber, indicating that the specimens were not appropriately fastened. Failure near the grip and lower strain rate values were also noted in both instances where rubber was introduced.

a) Stress-strain behaviour b) Failure mode

Figure 10: Effect of grip material

Numerical Findings

A comparison of the experimental and numerical stress-strain behaviours of the textile at the 0.2/s and 2/s strain rates are shown in Figure 11. In both instances, it is evident that the numerical results and experimental results agree.

Figures 12 and 13 depict the actual and simulated textile at the point of maximum strength. In Figure 12a and Figure 13a, the material was stretched to its ultimate elongation at this point without noticeable signs of specimen damage. The wire and lamina models displayed uniform stress along the rovings and lamina surfaces, while the grid models demonstrated maximum stress along the warp rovings and narrowing deformation of the weft rovings.

The models' computational costs and accuracies are shown in Table 3. Overall, the models were more than 99% accurate and were analysed with little computational effort. The longest and shortest analysis times were 34s and 0.3s for M3 and M1, respectively. The M1-Wire model demonstrated the highest accuracy for both strain rates with minimal computational effort. The accuracy and computational efficiency of the M2-lamina and M3-Grid models' were comparable.

Figure 11: Experimental and numerical results of the textile's stress-strain behaviour

a) Experimental b) M1-Wire c) M2-Lamina d) M3-Grid

Figure 12: Point at the ultimate stress of the textile at 0.2/s

a) Experimental b) M1-Wire c) M2-Lamina d) M3-Grid

Figure 13: Point at the ultimate stress of the textile at 2/s

Table 3: Comparison of computational cost and accuracy

Model	M1-Wire		M2-Lamina		M3-Grid	
Strain-rate	0.2/s	2/s	0.2/s	2/s	0.2/s	2/s
Computational cost						
CPU time [s]	3.8	0.3	10.9	1	9.6	0.5
Wall clock time [s]	7	2	20	3	34	18
Accuracy						
Strain [%]	99.97	99.97	99.60	99.97	99.72	99.96
Ultimate Strength [%]	99.99	99.96	99.54	99.98	99.72	99.87

CONCLUSION

An experimental and numerical investigation of the dynamic tensile behaviour of a basalt TRM textile was presented. The mechanical properties of the basalt textile varied with the strain rate. An increase in strain rate resulted in reduced elastic modulus, marginal reduction in average strength and an increase in the ultimate strain. Overall, the textile exhibited a linear elastic behaviour with brittle failure. Failure in the specimens initiated in the external rovings then progressed to the middle ones. The textile's stress-strain behaviour, failure mode and location, and strain rate were influenced by the type of material used in the grip area. It was also found that clamp grips and coupon specimens with aluminium tabs were unsuitable for the dynamic testing of this material. Numerical simulations aligned well with experimental results, and computational analyses demonstrated high accuracy and efficiency. The results improved our understanding of the behaviour of basalt textiles under varying strain rates, particularly their dynamic tensile mechanical properties, and emphasised the significance of grip material selection for accurate testing. Successful numerical simulations demonstrated the viability of using computational models to forecast the textile's stress-strain behaviour. Further dynamic testing at other strain-rate ranges can help to improve our understanding of basalt textile performance.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.